

Original article

A microRNA profile of the saliva in the argasid ticks *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata* and prediction of specific target genes

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ABSTRACT

Ornithodoros erraticus and *Ornithodoros moubata* ticks are the main vectors of the agents of human relapsing fever (TBRF) and African swine fever (ASF) in the Mediterranean Basin and Africa, respectively. Tick saliva is crucial for complete tick feeding and pathogen transmission, as it contains numerous molecules such as proteins, lipids, and non-coding RNAs (ncRNA) including microRNAs (miRNA). MiRNAs are small ncRNAs capable of regulating the expression of their target messenger RNA (mRNA) leading to degradation or inhibition of its translation into protein. Research on miRNAs from ixodid ticks has revealed that miRNAs are involved in the regulation of different physiological processes of ticks, as well as in the modulation of host gene expression, immune response to tick bite and pathogen transmission. Regarding argasid ticks, there is not information about their miRNAs or their potential involvement in tick physiology and/or in the regulation of the tick-host-pathogen interactions. The aim of this work was to profile the miRNAs expressed in the saliva of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*, and the *in silico* prediction and functional analysis of their target genes in the swine host. As a whole, up to 72 conserved miRNAs families were identified in both species: 35 of them were shared and 23 and 14 families were unique to *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*, respectively. The most abundant miRNAs families were mir-1, mir-10 and let-7 in *O. erraticus* and let-7, mir-252, mir-10 in *O. moubata*. Four miRNAs sequences of each species were validated by RT-qPCR confirming their presence in the saliva. Target gene prediction in the host (*Sus scrofa*) and functional analysis showed that the selected miRNAs are mainly involved in processes related to signal transduction, regulation of mRNA transcription and gene expression, synapse regulation, immune response, angiogenesis and vascular development. These results suggest that miRNAs could play an important role at the tick-host interface, providing new insights into this complex relationship that may contribute to a more precise selection of tick molecules for the development of therapeutic and immune strategies to control tick infestations and tick-borne pathogens.

1. Introduction

Ticks are haematophagous arthropods belonging to two main families, Ixodidae (hard ticks) and Argasidae (soft ticks). There are notable morphological and biological differences between these families. Both families have great medical and veterinary importance because they cause direct damage to the host but, mainly, because they transmit a large number of pathogens that affect livestock, companion animals and people worldwide (Arias et al., 2018; Talagrand-Reboul et al., 2018). Among argasid ticks, several species of the genus *Ornithodoros* stand out as vectors of two serious diseases, namely human relapsing fever (TBRF) and African swine fever (ASF). In particular, *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata* are the main vectors of the agents of ASF and TBRF

in the Mediterranean Basin and Africa, respectively (Vial, 2009; Boinas et al., 2014).

To successfully complete their blood feeding, haematophagous arthropods, including ticks, must overcome the haemostatic, inflammatory, immune and wound-healing responses deployed by the host, after the bite, in order to stop blood loss, to fight invading pathogens and to repair damaged tissues and vessels (Arcà and Ribeiro, 2018; Aounallah et al., 2020; Kitsou et al., 2021). For this, ticks and non-tick haematophagous arthropods have evolved a complex salivary fluid that includes anti-haemostatics, anti-inflammatory agents and immune modulators, which is inoculated at the bite site during feeding. This saliva modulates the host defensive responses, allowing the haematophagous vector to feed to engorgement, simultaneously favouring the

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transmission and establishing of vector-borne pathogens. Tick saliva contains hundreds of proteins, most of them with as yet unknown functions, as well as non-proteinaceous components, such as lipids (prostaglandins and prostacyclin) and non-coding RNA sequences (ncRNA) including microRNAs (miRNA) (Arcà and Ribeiro, 2018; Aounallah et al., 2020). miRNAs are small non-coding, single-stranded RNAs, between 19 and 24 nucleotides (nt) long, which can regulate the expression of their target genes by binding to messenger RNA (mRNA). This binding results in partial inhibition of the target mRNA translation and/or mRNA degradation. These molecules are conserved among different organisms and they possess a 2–7 nt region called the ‘seed’ at the 5’ region necessary to match to the 3’-untranslated region (UTR) sequence of the target mRNA. It is now well established that miRNAs play key regulatory roles in most biological processes, including the physiological and pathological ones (Bartel, 2009; Pasquinelli, 2012). miRNA biogenesis is a multi-step process that takes place in the nucleus and the cytoplasm of the cell. It starts with transcription of genomic DNA into long primary segments of up to 1 kbase (kb), known as primary miRNAs (pri-miRNAs). These molecules form ‘hairpin-stem-loop’ structures, which are cleaved in the nucleus by Drosha, an RNase III endonuclease. Drosha cuts both strands at sites near the base of the primary hairpin structure, generating 60–70 nt products called pre-miRNAs. The pre-miRNAs are actively exported to the cytoplasm by the action of the enzyme exportin-5. In the cytoplasm, the pre-miRNAs are cut by a second RNase III enzyme, DICER, giving rise to double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) sequences of about 20–25 nt in length (Lee et al., 2002, 2003; Denli et al., 2004; Fabian et al., 2010). Mature single-stranded miRNAs are generated from these dsRNAs by the action of a helicase. Mature miRNAs are incorporated into the ribonucleoprotein complex known as the RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC), which is the catalytic machinery responsible for the degradation and/or inhibition of translation of the target mRNAs (He et al., 2004; Riolo et al., 2020).

In recent years, newly developed molecular biology and next-generation sequencing technologies have contributed significant knowledge regarding the complex interactions that take place at the vector–pathogen–host interface, allowing elucidation of the relevant role that miRNAs play in the processes of vector attachment, blood feeding and pathogen transmission (Aounallah et al., 2020; Kitsou et al., 2021).

Most research on the biological role of miRNAs in haematophagous vectors has been conducted in mosquitoes because of their role as primary vectors for a range of severe human diseases (reviewed by Xu et al., 2021). Although ticks are also vectors of important human and animal pathogens, there have been a few studies related to their miRNAs. These available studies have involved nine ixodid tick species and have focused on: (i) the identification of the miRNAs expressed in different tick tissues, developmental stages and physiological conditions, and (ii) analysis of the role played by these miRNAs in the regulation of important physiological processes of ticks. These processes include moulting (Wu et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2020); blood digestion, egg laying and hatching (Hao et al., 2017; Malik et al., 2019a, 2019b); response to stimuli (Wang et al., 2015; Luo et al., 2019); development and life cycle (Barrero et al., 2017; Luo et al., 2021; J. 2022) and regulation of cold tolerance (Agwunobi et al., 2021). Some additional studies have examined how miRNAs regulate the tick–pathogen relationship. They have shown that *Ixodes scapularis* miRNAs facilitate transmission of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*, *Borrelia burgdorferi* sensu stricto and Powassan virus, and thus helping to establish the infection (Artigas-Jerónimo et al., 2019; Hermance et al., 2019; Ramasamy et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2022). Apart from these studies, only one has investigated tick miRNA-mediated regulation of vertebrate host gene expression at the tick–host interface (Hackenberg et al., 2017). These authors conducted an *in silico* prediction of potential gene targets in the vertebrate host and showed that *Ixodes ricinus* saliva miRNAs can modulate vertebrate host homeostasis. These miRNAs are seemingly

secreted in the saliva via exosomes and released into the host cells to manipulate gene expression and to deregulate host defense pathways (Hackenberg and Kotsyfakis, 2018).

Regarding argasid ticks, there is no information available about their miRNAs or their potential involvement in tick physiology and/or in the regulation of the tick–host–pathogen interface. As mentioned above, *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* transmit important pathogens that affect humans and swine throughout wide regions of Southern Europe and Africa (Oleaga-Pérez et al., 1990; Vial, 2009; Boinas et al., 2014; Talagrand-Reboul et al., 2018). The presence of these ticks in anthropic environments makes it extremely difficult to eradicate TBRF and ASF from endemic areas, increasing the constant threat of their re-introduction in the countries from which they have been eradicated, and contributes to their persistence in countries affected by these diseases. Reasonably, a better understanding of the biology of both species could lead to the development of new effective control measures that contribute to the elimination of *Ornithodoros* tick populations.

In the light of the above, we hypothesised that the miRNAs expressed in the *Ornithodoros* tick saliva have important roles in regulating *Ornithodoros*–host relationships. Accordingly, we aimed to profile the miRNAs expressed in the saliva of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* and to perform *in silico* prediction and functional analysis of their target genes in the swine host. Herein, we report the sequencing of the small ncRNAs present in both *Ornithodoros* saliva, the identification of 72 conserved miRNA families, and the swine genes predicted to be targeted by these miRNAs. The functional analysis of the target genes reveals that they would be involved in biological processes relevant for tick–host relationships. The present study provides the first data on miRNAs expressed in argasid saliva and the likely regulation of gene targets in the host.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Ticks

The adult female ticks used in this study, of the species *O. moubata* and *O. erraticus*, came from two colonies maintained at the Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiological of Salamanca (IRNASA, CSIC). The *O. moubata* colony was established from specimens kindly provided by Dr Philip Wilkinson (Institute for Animal Health, Pirbright, United Kingdom), originally captured in Malawi. The *O. erraticus* colony was obtained from specimens captured in the province of Salamanca, Spain. Ticks regularly fed on New Zealand White rabbits and were maintained in a culture chamber at 28 °C, 85% relative humidity, and a 12-h photoperiod. Animal experiments were performed in accordance with the regulation established by the Ethical and Animal Welfare Committee of IRNASA and the Ethical Committee of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC, Spain) and met the corresponding European Union legislation (Directive 2010/63/EU).

2.2. Tick saliva collection

Ornithodoros moubata and *O. erraticus* saliva samples were obtained from newly moulted female ticks. Saliva was collected as described previously by R. Pérez-Sánchez et al. (2022). First, unfed female ticks from both species were washed by sequential immersion and shaking in the following solutions: tap water, 3% hydrogen peroxide, two washes in distilled water, 70% ethanol and two more washes in distilled water. Thereafter, specimens were dried on paper towels and immobilised ventral side up with double-sided adhesive tape on a glass plate in groups of five ticks, for a better manipulation. Each tick was micro-injected with 0.5 µL of 2% pilocarpine hydrochloride (Sigma Chemical) in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) through the genital pore, using a 5 µL Hamilton syringe (33 G and 25 mm long). A few seconds after stimulation, tick chelicerae started to move and small droplets of clear viscous saliva were secreted. Then, the saliva was

collected continuously from the mouthparts, using a micropipette tip containing a small amount of ice-cold PBS, and deposited into an ice-cold tube with QIAzol Lysis Reagent (Qiagen). This process was repeated until perceptible emission stopped, usually 15–20 min after stimulation. Three replicates of each species were prepared, containing the secretion from 25 female *O. moubata* per sample (OM1, OM2 and OM3) or 50 female *O. erraticus* per sample (OE1, OE2 and OE3). Saliva samples were centrifuged 10 min at 10,000 rpm at 4 °C, and the supernatant was recovered and stored at –80 °C until used for RNA extraction.

2.3. RNA purification and sequencing

Library preparation (three for each tick species) and sequencing were carried out at the Genomics Services of the Fundación Parque Científico de Madrid (Spain) (<https://fpcm.es/en/servicios-cientificos/>). Small RNA was extracted from the saliva samples using the miRNeasy Serum/Plasma Kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer's instructions. This kit allows efficient purification of RNA < 200 nt, such as miRNA, from a small volume of fluid. RNA was eluted in 14 µL of RNase-free water and RNA quality and concentration were assessed with a 2200 TapeStation system (Agilent Technologies) using an RNA ScreenTape. Then, 30 ng of total RNA from each sample was used as input for library preparation with the NEBNext® Multiplex Small RNA Library Prep Set for Illumina (New England Biolabs; catalog number E7300S) following manufacturer's recommendations.

The resulting libraries were validated and quantified with the TapeStation and D1000 ScreenTape and an equimolecular pool was made. Afterwards, libraries were run in a 6% acrylamide gel electrophoresis and the region corresponding to small RNA (135–330 base pairs [bp]) was selected and assessed using an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer with High-Sensitivity DNA chips. The final libraries were titrated by quantitative polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using the Kapa-SYBR FAST qPCR kit for Light Cycler 480 and a reference standard for quantification. The library pool was denatured and seeded on a NovaSeq SP flow cell (Illumina), where clusters were formed and sequenced in a 1 × 100 single-read sequencing run on a NovaSeq 6000 sequencer using a flow cell SP v1.5 (Illumina).

2.4. Bioinformatics analysis

After sequencing, 16–28 million (mean 20.4×10^6) single-end reads were obtained per sample (Table 1). Quality control of sequences was performed with FastQC (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>). Using the program Prinseq (Schmieder and Edwards, 2011), Fastq files were filtered for quality (PHRED > 24) and size (≥ 18 nt), reads with > 5% sequence ambiguities (Ns) were removed and adaptors were trimmed using the Cutadapt tool (Martin, 2011). Next, processed reads from each sample were mapped to a eukaryotic ncRNA database in RNACentral (<https://rnacentral.org/>) (Griffiths-Jones, 2019) and read alignment was conducted with Bowtie2 (Langmead and Salzberg, 2012). Taxonomic annotation was performed with BLAST (Altschul et al., 1990) using a precompiled database from

National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) of prokaryotic and eukaryotic organisms. After this processing, the ribosomal RNA (rRNA) and transfer RNA (tRNA) sequences, together with the sequences of bacteria, fungi and viruses identified in the samples, were discarded/excluded. Finally, redundant sequences above an identity threshold of 99.5% were discarded using the CD-HIT program (Fu et al., 2012). Read counts were obtained using Corset (Davidson and Oshlack, 2014) and expression values were calculated as counts per million (CPM).

Finally, to analyze the salivary miRNA, only sequences identified in all three salivary samples of each species were considered.

This bioinformatics analysis was carried out at the Biotechvana of the Scientific Park, University of Valencia (Spain).

2.5. Validation of miRNA-Seq results by reverse transcription-quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR)

To validate the miRNA-seq results, four miRNA sequences from each species were selected for RT-qPCR validation. The selection was based on the miRNA abundance value. For this assay, three fresh saliva samples were obtained from each species and the fractions of small RNAs were purified as described in Section 2.3.

The synthetic control templates RNA spike-ins UniSp2, UniSp5 and UniSp6 (miRCURY LNA RNA Spike-in kit, Qiagen) and the matching primer pairs for their detection are included in this assay to provide controls for the quality of the RNA isolation, the complementary DNA (cDNA) synthesis reaction and the PCR amplification. UniSp2 and UniSp5 were added to the saliva samples before miRNA isolation, as a quality control of this step, and UniSp6 was included in the RT reaction as an endogenous control. cDNA was synthesised from the three samples of saliva from each tick species (six samples total) using the miRCURY LNA RT Kit (Qiagen) including 6 µL of purified miRNA. Amplification reactions were done in 96-well plates with the miRCURY LNA SYBR Green PCR Kit (Qiagen) using the following settings: 2 min at 95 °C for initial heat activation followed by 40 cycles of 10 s at 95 °C and 56 °C for 60 s. Each sample was replicated three times. All miRNA primers were custom made by Qiagen using the miRCURY LNA miRNA PCR Assay (Qiagen). Supplementary Table 1 shows the miRNA sequences from which primers were designed and the corresponding primer codes assigned by Qiagen. All procedures were performed by following the manufacturer's instructions and amplification was performed using the ABI PRISM 7900HT Fast Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems). The PCR products were run in a 2% agarose gel electrophoresis and visualised with GelRead Nucleic Acid Staining Solution (Biotium).

2.6. miRNA target prediction in the host *SUS scrofa*

miRNAs regulate gene expression by binding to the 3'-UTR of mRNA targets. Prediction of the *O. moubata* and *O. erraticus* miRNA target genes in the host *S. scrofa* was done with the miRNAconsTarget program from sRNAtoolbox (<https://arn.ugr.es/srnatoolbox/amirconstarget>) (Rueda et al., 2015; Aparicio-Puerta et al., 2019), which employs four programs: simple seed analysis, miRanda (John et al., 2004), TargetSpy (Sturm

Table 1

Summary of sequence data and alignment to eukaryotic ncRNA of RNACentral database in *O. erraticus* (OE1, OE2 and OE3) and *O. moubata* (OM1, OM2 and OM3) saliva samples.

	OE1	OE2	OE3	OM1	OM2	OM3
Raw reads	28,065,832	19,908,691	21,179,633	17,435,679	19,099,318	16,870,462
Preprocessed reads	25,854,159	18,492,110	19,696,964	15,865,621	17,810,158	15,314,478
Reads mapped (%)	20,336,225 (78.66%)	10,573,132 (57.18%)	11,339,253 (57.57%)	13,424,321 (84.61%)	15,446,275 (86.73%)	13,131,320 (85.74%)
Reads corresponding to rRNA and tRNA	16,829,653	8086,808	9221,010	10,156,773	10,938,742	10,009,081
Reads from bacteria-fungi-viruses	1422,387	477,998	262,971	1848,193	2597,199	1555,395
Total reads of non-coding RNA sequences in tick saliva	650,756	1163,104	1037,027	851,059	662,847	510,455

et al., 2010) and PITA (Kertesz et al., 2007). Target gene prediction was conducted for the eight miRNAs previously validated by RT-qPCR by using the 3'-UTR region from the *S. scrofa* mRNA transcripts obtained from the NCBI (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov) (assembly accession: GCF_000003025.6). To reduce the high number of false-positive target predictions, only host transcripts targeted by all four programs were considered.

Next, the identified target genes were subjected to a functional analysis. Target genes were mapped to GO terms in the Gene Ontology (GO) database (Carbon et al., 2009) (<http://geneontology.org/>), and an enrichment analysis was carried out regarding Pathways (KEGG, Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes), Biological Process and Molecular Function using the ShinyGO web application (<http://bioinformatics.sdstate.edu/go/>) (Ge et al., 2020; Kanehisa et al., 2021).

3. Results

3.1. Deep sequencing of small RNAs from saliva of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*

All saliva samples were obtained, following the same procedures, from unfed adult female ticks of the same age and physiological condition. We constructed six small RNA libraries, corresponding to three biological replicates of each tick species, and sequenced them using Illumina technology.

After quality filtering, adapter trimming and size selection (≥ 18 nt), there were 15–25 million reads for mapping to the eukaryotic ncRNA database in RNACentral. Table 1 shows the number of original reads (raw data) and pre-processed reads suitable for analysis. For both species, read mapping success was $> 57\%$ in all replicas, with an average of 64.47% for *O. erraticus* and 85.69% for *O. moubata*. After mapping, the sequences corresponding to rRNAs, tRNAs and viral, bacterial and fungal sequences were all filtered and excluded from the analysis. The resulting number of reads corresponding to small ncRNA tick sequences

Fig. 1. Distribution of small ncRNAs among different categories identified in *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata*. The number of sequences in each group and the proportion that it represents are indicated. Only categories with more than 25 sequences have been represented (see Supplementary Table 2).

was $650\text{--}1037 \times 10^3$ for *O. erraticus* and $510\text{--}851 \times 10^3$ for *O. moubata* (Table 1).

The CD-HIT tool clustered sequences with > 99.5% identity, resulting in the filtering and selection of 3114 and 3997 small ncRNAs from *O. moubata* and *O. erraticus*, respectively (Supplementary Table 2). These sequences were classified into different categories of small ncRNA (Supplementary Table 2). Fig. 1 shows the distribution of ncRNA categories, with more than 25 sequences, for each species, including the number of sequences in each category and their ratio (%) with respect to the total sequences mapped. This distribution was very similar in both species. The number of sequences annotated as miRNAs represented 12%–13% of the total sequences mapped. Among the remaining categories, the sequences annotated as miscellaneous RNA (miscRNA) were the most numerous, accounting for 50% and 51% in *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*, respectively, followed by small RNA regulators, which represented 16% and 18%, respectively, and small nuclear RNA (snRNA), which represented 8% and 12%, respectively.

3.2. Size distribution

We analysed the reads mapped to the RNACentral database – except those representing rRNA, tRNA and viral, bacterial and fungal sequences – for length distribution. Most small ncRNA reads were 18–25 nt, with the highest number of reads at 18 nt, corresponding to 493 and 681 sequences from *O. moubata* and *O. erraticus*, respectively (Fig. 2A). Regarding the length of sequences annotated as miRNAs, the most frequent were 22–24 nt in *O. moubata* and 22–25 nt in *O. erraticus*. There was also a relatively high number of 26–28 nt sequences in *O. erraticus* (Fig. 2B).

3.3. Identification and characterization of salivary miRNAs in *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*

As mentioned in Section 2, for the specific analysis of salivary miRNAs, only the sequences that were identified in the three replicated saliva samples have been considered. Overall, up to 72 conserved miRNA families were identified in both *Ornithodoros* species. Of these, 35 were shared by both species, and 23 and 14 families were unique to *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*, respectively (Fig. 3A).

It should be noted that the miRNA families identified exclusively in one or the other species correspond, in most cases, to unique sequences with a low expression level (Supplementary Tables 3 and 4). Thus, it is possible that some sequences with low expression may have not been detected because they are masked by more abundant sequences/families with higher expression. This possibility suggests that some of the observed differences in the miRNA profiles between the species could be

artefacts, and the real differences in miRNA profiles between species would be lower (Ouyang et al., 2019).

In *O. erraticus* saliva, there were 58 conserved miRNA families accounting for 388 unique sequences. Among them, the top seven families annotated were mir-1, mir-10, let-7, mir-184, mir-279, mir-7 and mir-71; all of these families were also present in *O. moubata*. The conserved miRNA families annotated as the mir-1, mir-10 and let-7 families displayed the highest numbers of putative isomiRs, specifically 54, 42 and 36 sequences, respectively (Fig. 3B, Supplementary Table 3). Similarly, in the saliva of *O. moubata*, there were 49 conserved miRNA families accounting for 161 unique sequences. Among them, the top six were let-7, mir-252, mir-10, mir-7, mir-279 and mir-71; all of these families were also present in the saliva of *O. erraticus*, although with fewer sequences (Fig. 3C, Supplementary Table 4).

Fig. 4 shows the 25 sequences/isomiRs with the highest expression in each species. In *O. erraticus*, these sequences were annotated as mir-279 (16 sequences), mir-252 (3 sequences), mir-75 (4 sequences), mir-1 (1 sequence) and mir-276 (1 sequence) families. The highest expression levels corresponded to mir-279_17 and mir-279_21 with 2987 and 2438 CPM respectively; the remaining miRNAs showed expression levels between 1100 and 1800 CPM (Fig. 4A, Supplementary Table 3).

In *O. moubata*, the sequences with the highest expression corresponded to the mir-252 (8 sequences), mir-375 (6 sequences), mir-279 (5 sequences), mir-3931 (2 sequences), mir-750 (2 sequences), mir-34 (1 sequence) and mir-X18 (1 sequence) families (Fig. 4B). In this species, the identified miRNAs showed significantly higher expression than the miRNAs identified in *O. erraticus*, particularly mir-252_2, mir-252_3 and mir-252_4, which showed CPM values > 55,000. For the rest of the sequences, the CPM values were lower, but they were still high for mir-X18, mir-375_1, mir-375_2, mir-375_3, mir-252_1 and mir-375_4, with expression levels between 10,000 and 25,000 CPM (Fig. 4B, Supplementary Table 4).

3.4. Validation of miRNA expression

We performed RT-qPCR analysis for a set of selected miRNAs to validate the RNA-seq results. We selected eight miRNA sequences (four from each species) among those annotated with the highest expression levels: mir-279_17, mir-252_6, mir-750_6 and mir-1_38 from *O. erraticus*, and mir-252_2, mir-X18, mir-375_1 and mir-375_4 from *O. moubata*. The results of this analysis are summarised in Fig. 5, which shows the amplification plots and Ct values for each miRNA, and the agarose gels with the corresponding amplicons from all saliva samples. Individual amplification data are compiled in Supplementary Tables 5 and 6. It is evident that all miRNAs were amplified efficiently in all biological and technical replicates. The Ct values were between 16.26 and 25.73 for

Fig. 2. Length distribution analysis of all tick small ncRNA sequences (A) and tick miRNA sequences (B) in *Ornithodoros erraticus* (blue) and *Ornithodoros moubata* (orange).

Fig. 3. (A) miRNAs families jointly identified in *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata*. (B) miRNAs families identified in *O. erraticus* and (C) in *O. moubata*. Only families containing more than one sequence identified are represented.

Fig.. 4. Expression level in counts per million (CPM) of the 30 more abundant isomiRs in (A) *Ornithodoros erraticus* and (B) *Ornithodoros moubata*.

Fig. 5. Amplification plots of RT-qPCR assay and agarose gels showing amplicons in the triplicated saliva samples from *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata*.

Fig. 6. Number of host (*Sus scrofa*) target genes predicted for each miRNA and Venn diagrams depicting the degree of overlap among targeted genes by *Ornithodoros erraticus* (A) and *Ornithodoros moubata* (B) miRNAs.

O. erraticus and between 23.40 and 30.09 for *O. moubata*. Supplementary Fig. 1 shows the amplification plots of the RNA spike-ins, UniSp2, UniSp5 and UniSp6, used as technical control templates. These results confirm the presence of these miRNAs in the saliva of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* and the correctness of their sequences obtained by RNA-seq.

3.5. miRNA target gene prediction and functional analysis

Identifying the interactions between the miRNAs and their target genes is a key step to define the function played by miRNAs in the complex molecular networks that regulate the biological processes in tick physiology and tick–host–pathogen relationships. Accordingly, to investigate the role of the *Ornithodoros* salivary miRNAs in the tick–host relationship and tick regulation of the host defensive responses, we conducted an *in silico* prediction of potential target genes for the eight salivary miRNAs (four from each species) previously validated by RT-qPCR. As mentioned previously, several algorithms for target gene prediction, together with databases containing miRNA–target information, have been developed. However, the currently available computational prediction tools still predict large numbers of false-positive

targets. To reduce the false positives as much as possible, we have applied four prediction tools and considered as true positives only the targets predicted by all the four algorithms.

The miRNA target gene prediction results are shown in Fig. 6A and 6B and Supplementary Table 7. For the four miRNAs from *O. erraticus*, a total of 3114 unique target genes were predicted: 1494 genes targeted by mir-252_6, 1142 genes targeted by mir-1_38, 819 genes targeted by mir-750_6, and 614 genes targeted by mir-279_17 (Fig. 6A). The Venn diagram in Fig. 6A shows the overlap between the predicted target genes. As a whole, 777 genes were predicted to be targeted by two or more of the miRNAs tested. However, for each particular miRNA, > 50% of their target genes were not predicted as targets of the remaining miRNAs tested (Fig. 6A).

Regarding the four miRNAs from *O. moubata*, a total of 2308 unique target genes were predicted: 1530 genes targeted by mir-252_2, 167 genes targeted by mir-375_1, 143 genes targeted by mir-375_4, and 774 genes targeted by mir-X18 (Fig. 6B). In this species, no genes were predicted as targets for all four miRNAs tested, and most of the predicted targets corresponded to a single miRNA (Fig. 6B).

Following the target gene prediction, we conducted GO and KEGG

Fig. 7. Significantly enriched pathways (KEGG database) for genes targeted by the *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata* miRNA. Only pathways with the highest fold enrichment values (up to a maximum of 10) are included in the graphs (see Supplementary Table 8).

pathway enrichment analysis. We considered only the biological and functional pathways presenting a false discovery rate (FDR) value < 0.05 to be significantly enriched. The complete results of this analysis are presented in Supplementary Table 8. Figs. 7, 8 and 9 show the significantly enriched pathways, biological processes and molecular functions, respectively, with the highest fold enrichment values (up to a maximum of 10).

Pathway enrichment analysis revealed that target genes of mir-750_6, mir-252_6, mir-1_38, mir-X18 and mir-252_2 are over-represented in 18 KEGG pathways (Fig. 7). Target genes of isomiRs of the mir-252 family (mir-252_6 and mir-252_2) are involved in several pathways related to the nervous system such as ‘dopaminergic synapse,’ ‘glutamatergic synapse’ and ‘long-term potentiation’. Likewise, target genes of mi-1_38, mir-252_6 and mir-252_2 are involved in processes related to signal transduction such as ‘ErbB signaling pathway,’ ‘phosphatidylinositol signaling system,’ ‘Wnt signaling pathway’ and ‘Hedgehog signaling pathway’. Other significantly enriched pathways are ‘regulation of actin cytoskeleton,’ ‘adherens junction,’ ‘glycan biosynthesis,’ ‘cancer’ and ‘infectious diseases’ (Fig. 7). All the pathways enriched in genes targeted by mir-279_17, mir-375_1 and mir-375_4 showed FDR values > 0.05 and, consequently, we did not consider them.

Similarly, enrichment analysis showed that target genes of mir-750_6, mir-279_17, mir-252_6, mir-1_38, mir-X18, mir-252_2 and mir-375_1 are significantly overrepresented in 269 GO biological processes. Among the biological processes with higher fold enrichment values, which are represented in Fig. 8, we highlight the following: (i) those related to cytoskeleton organization and vesicle-mediated transport such as ‘regulation of actin filament,’ ‘actin polymerisation’ and ‘receptor-mediated endocytosis’ (mir-1_38); (ii) processes related to regulation of gene expression and signal transduction such as ‘miRNA loading onto RISC involved in gene silencing by miRNA,’ ‘small RNA loading onto RISC’ and ‘regulation of Rac protein signal transduction’ (mir-279_17, mir-252_6 and mir-252_2); and (iii) processes related to system development such as ‘circulatory system process,’ ‘lung cell differentiation’ and ‘positive regulation of heart growth’ (mir-279_17 and mir-750_6) (Fig. 8). All biological processes enriched in the target genes of the mir-375_4 showed FDR values > 0.05 and, consequently, we did not consider them.

The enrichment analysis also detected that the identified genes are significantly overrepresented in 76 molecular functions of the GO database. Among the molecular functions with higher fold enrichment values, which are represented in Fig. 9, we highlight the following: (i) functions related to binding (i.e. nucleic acids, proteins, lipids, etc.) such as ‘adenylate cyclase binding,’ ‘profilin binding,’ ‘sequence-specific DNA binding,’ and ‘purine-rich negative regulatory element binding’ (mir-375_1, mir-279_17, mir-252_6 and mir-252_2); (ii) functions related to kinase and transferase activity such as ‘AMP-activated protein kinase activity,’ ‘RNA polymerase II CTD heptapeptide repeat kinase activity,’ ‘eukaryotic translation initiation factor 2 alpha kinase activity’ and ‘phosphotransferase activity, alcohol group as acceptor’ (mir-279_17, mir-375_1, mir-X18 and mir-252_2); (iii) functions related to transcription and translation regulation such as ‘DNA-binding transcription factor activity, RNA polymerase II-specific’ and ‘translation regulator activity’ (mir-279_17 and mir-252_6); and (iv) functions related to transporter activity such as ‘organic acid:sodium symporter activity,’ ‘short-chain fatty acid transmembrane transporter activity’ and ‘cation transmembrane transporter activity’ (mir-1_38, mir-252_6 and mir-X18). All molecular functions enriched in the target genes of the mir-375_4 showed FDR values > 0.05 and, consequently, we did not consider them.

Additionally, to reduce the number of putative false-positive predictions, we conducted a deeper analysis of only 29 transcripts targeted by at least four of the eight miRNAs tested (and predicted by the four algorithms used) (Table 2 and Supplementary Table 9). Table 2 shows that a high ratio of the predicted target host proteins would be involved in biological processes important for the host–tick relationships. Around

50% of the target genes could be related to signal transduction, regulation of mRNA transcription and gene expression (i.e. adenylate cyclase 10, host cell factor C2 and Kruppel-like factor C2). Other biological processes that seem to be regulated by tick miRNAs are those related to synapse regulation (glutamate ionotropic receptor, soluble carrier family 7 and ATPase family AAA domain) and the immune response (TRAF-interacting protein and growth hormone secretagogue receptor). In addition, we can point out the regulation of the chondromodulin gene because it is potentially involved in angiogenesis and endothelial cell proliferation, and thus it may be related to tick attachment and the vascular and endothelial mechanisms underlying blood intake (Shukunami and Hiraki, 2007) (Table 2).

4. Discussion

Tick saliva inoculated in the host during feeding contains a repertoire of bioactive molecules, including miRNAs, which play key roles in tick attachment, blood ingestion and pathogen transmission. Salivary miRNAs are thought to play significant roles in these processes because they participate in the post-transcriptional regulation of specific target genes at the tick–host–pathogen interface (Bensaoud et al., 2019; Aunallah et al., 2020; Kitsou et al., 2021).

The sialomes of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* have recently been published, contributing to a broad understanding of tick proteins expressed in the salivary glands and saliva (Oleaga et al., 2021a, 2021b; Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2021; R. 2022). However, until the present study, there had been no information about the salivary miRNAs from these two species, or from any other argasid tick species. For this reason, we found it interesting to study the miRNAs of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* and to carry out the *in silico* prediction and functional analysis of their target genes in their host *S. scrofa*.

Some authors have already advised that obtaining saliva samples in optimal conditions is a critical point to carry out these experiments (Nawaz et al., 2020). Saliva collection is a laborious process in which preserving the integrity of the RNA sequences may be difficult. Indeed, Arcà et al. (2019) described that the miRNA sequences in mosquito saliva samples obtained by a similar procedure (stimulation with pilocarpine) show a smaller size than usual (14–16 nt), which they attributed to the degradation of the miRNA sequences during the laborious process of obtaining the samples. The *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* saliva samples we obtained seem to have been well preserved because the size distribution analysis of the miRNA sequences showed the expected length range. We found that > 62% of the sequences were 18–24 nt in length, which is consistent with the typical size of salivary miRNAs of ticks (Malik et al., 2019a). However, it seems that RNA degradation was not completely avoided because the high abundance of sequences annotated as rRNA was probably due to partial degradation of large rRNAs during saliva collection.

We constructed six small RNA libraries from the saliva of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*, obtaining 15–26 million reads per library, figures that are in the range of those obtained by Malik et al. (2019a) when they sequenced the salivary small RNAs from *Haemaphysalis longicornis*. To give our results greater robustness, we only analysed the miRNA sequences annotated in the three biological replicates of each species. With this approach, for *O. moubata* we identified 162 isomiRs clustered in 49 miRNA families; for *O. erraticus* we identified 388 isomiRs clustered in 58 miRNA families (Supplementary Tables 3 and 4). Numerous miRNAs identified here in the saliva of *Ornithodoros* spp. have been identified previously in the saliva and salivary glands of the ixodid ticks *I. ricinus*, *I. scapularis*, *Rhipicephalus microplus* and *H. longicornis* (Barrero et al., 2011; Zhou et al., 2013; Hackenberg et al., 2017; Hermance et al., 2019; Malik et al., 2019a). Moreover, almost half of the miRNAs we detected have also been found in extracellular vesicles (EVs) in *H. longicornis* saliva (Nawaz et al., 2020), suggesting that salivary miRNAs of argasids, as those of ixodids and mosquitoes, would also be transported in saliva inside EVs (Bensaoud et al., 2019).

Fig. 8. Significantly enriched Biological Processes (Gene Ontology database) for genes targeted by the *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata* miRNA. Only Biological Processes with the highest fold enrichment values (up to a maximum of 10) are included in the graphs (see Supplementary Table 8).

Fig. 9. Significantly enriched Molecular Functions (Gene Ontology database) for genes targeted by the *Ornithodoros erraticus* and *Ornithodoros moubata* miRNAs. Only Molecular Functions with the highest fold enrichment values (up to a maximum of 10) are included in the graphs (see Supplementary Table 8).

Table 2

Genes targeted by at least four miRNAs sequences identified in *O. erraticus* or in *O. moubata*, as classified by Biological Process of the Gene Ontology (GO) database. In order to differentiate the mRNAs corresponding to each species, the miRNAs that have been identified in the saliva of *O. erraticus* are indicated in bold.

Gene name	Gene symbol	miRNAs	Biological Process (GO)	Molecular function (GO)
Signal transduction, regulation of mRNA transcription and other processes related with gene expression				
Adenylate cyclase 10	ADCY10	mir-279_17 , mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6	extracellular transport [GO:0006858]; RNA metabolic process [GO:0016070]; intracellular signal transduction [GO:0035556]	adenylate cyclase activity [GO:0,004,016]; bicarbonate binding [GO:0,071,890]
Bone morphogenetic protein 10	BMP10	mir-279_17 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18, mir-750_6	positive regulation of DNA-templated transcription [GO:0,045,893]; positive regulation of gene expression [GO:0,010,628]	glycosaminoglycan binding [GO:0,005,539]; transforming growth factor beta receptor activity [GO:0,005,024];
Calcium/calmodulin dependent protein kinase IV	CAMK4	mir-279_17 , mir-1_38 , mir-X18, mir-750_6	protein phosphorylation [GO:0,006,468]; positive regulation of DNA-templated transcription [GO:0,045,893]	ATP binding [GO:0,005,524]; protein kinase activity [GO:0,004,672]
Decapping mRNA 2	DCP2	mir-279_17 , mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6	nuclear-transcribed mRNA catabolic process, nonsense-mediated decay [GO:0,000,184]	enzyme activator activity [GO:0,008,047]; mRNA binding [GO:0,003,729]
Diacylglycerol kinase (DAG kinase) (EC 2.7.1.107)	DGKI	mir-279_17 , mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-750_6	Ras protein signal transduction [GO:0,007,265]; presynaptic modulation of chemical synaptic transmission [GO:0,099,171]	ATP binding [GO:0,005,524]; diacylglycerol kinase activity [GO:0,004,143]
Dual specificity tyrosine phosphorylation regulated kinase 2	DYRK2	mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-750_6	apoptotic process [GO:0,006,915]; signal transduction [GO:0,007,165]	ATP binding [GO:0,005,524]; magnesium ion binding [GO:0,000,287]; tyrosine kinase activity [GO:0,004,713]
Host cell factor C2	HCFC2	mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18, mir-375_4	regulation of gene expression [GO:0,010,468]	
Kruppel like factor 8	KLF8	mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-750_6	regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II [GO:0,006,357]	regulation of RNA biosynthetic process [GO:2,001,141]; transcription cis-regulatory region binding [GO:0000976]
Mastermind like transcriptional coactivator 2	MAML2	mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-750_6	positive regulation of transcription of Notch receptor target [GO:0,007,221]	transcription coactivator activity [GO:0,003,713]
NFE2 like bZIP transcription factor 3	NFE2L3	mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18, mir-750_6	regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II [GO:0,006,357]	DNA-binding transcription factor activity, RNA polymerase II-specific [GO:0,000,981];
Purine rich element binding protein A	PURA	mir-279_17 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18	DNA replication [GO:0006260]; lymphocyte proliferation [GO:0046651]; regulation of RNA biosynthetic process [GO: 2,001,141]; nervous system development [GO:0007399]; regulation of cellular process [GO:0050794]	regulation of gene expression [GO:0010468]; translation regulator activity [GO:0045182]; DNA binding [GO:0003677]; transcription regulator activity [GO:0140110]
SAFB like transcription modulator	SLTM	mir-279_17 , mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6	regulation of mRNA processing [GO:0,050,684]; regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II [GO:0,006,357]	RNA binding [GO:0,003,723]; sequence-specific DNA binding [GO:0,043,565]
SAP domain containing ribonucleoprotein	SARNP	mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18	regulation of gene expression [GO:0010468]; poly (A) ⁺ mRNA export from nucleus [GO:0016973]	chromatin binding [GO:0,003,682]
Tankyrase 2	TNKS2	mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18	regulation of signal transduction [GO:0009966]; positive regulation of telomere capping [GO:1,904,355]; protein poly-ADP-ribosylation [GO:0070212]	NAD ⁺ ADP-ribosyltransferase activity [GO:0,003,950]
Zinc finger protein 704	ZNF704	mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18, mir-750_6	regulation of transcription by RNA polymerase II [GO:0,006,357]	DNA-binding transcription factor activity [GO:0003700]; sequence-specific double-stranded DNA binding [GO:1,990,837]
Immune response				
TRAF interacting protein with forkhead associated domain	TIFA	mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18, mir-750_6	I-kappaB kinase/NF-kappaB signaling [GO:0,007,249]; innate immune response [GO:0,045,087];	
Growth hormone secretagogue receptor	GHSR	mir-279_17 , mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6	negative regulation of inflammatory response [GO:0050728]; negative regulation of interleukin-1 beta production [GO:0032691]; negative regulation of interleukin-6 production [GO:0032715]; negative regulation of tumor necrosis factor production [GO:0032720]	cytokine activity [GO:0,005,125]; metal ion binding [GO:0,046,872]; tumor necrosis factor receptor binding [GO:0,005,164]
Regulation of synapse				
Glutamate ionotropic receptor NMDA type subunit 2B	GRIN2B	mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-750_6	calcium ion transmembrane import into cytosol [GO:0,097,553]; regulation of neuronal synaptic plasticity [GO:0,048,168]	transmembrane transporter activity [GO:0022857]; signaling receptor activity [GO:0038023]
Solute carrier family 7 member 11	SLC7A11	mir-1_38 , mir-252_2, mir-252_6 , mir-X18	amino acid transport [GO:0,006,865]; regulation of synapse organization [GO:0,050,807]	transmembrane transporter activity [GO:0,022,857]

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Gene name	Gene symbol	miRNAs	Biological Process (GO)	Molecular function (GO)
ATPase family AAA domain containing 1	ATAD1	mir-279_17, mir-1_38, mir-252_2, mir-252_6	synaptic signaling [GO:0099536]; regulation of transport [GO:0051049]; postsynaptic endocytosis [GO:0140239]	ATP binding [GO:0,005,524]; ATP hydrolysis activity [GO:0,016,887]
Other				
Ankyrin repeat domain 34C	ANKRD34C	mir-1_38, mir-252_2, mir-252_6, mir-750_6	-	
Chondromodulin	CNMD	mir-1_38, mir-252_2, mir-252_6, mir-X18	negative regulation of angiogenesis [GO:0,016,525]; negative regulation of endothelial cell proliferation [GO:0,001,937]	
Family with sequence similarity 126 member A	FAM126A	mir-279_17, mir-252_2, mir-252_6, mir-750_6	phosphatidylinositol phosphate biosynthetic process [GO:0,046,854]; protein localization to plasma membrane [GO:0,072,659]	
Gametocyte specific factor 1	GTSF1	mir-279_17, mir-1_38, mir-252_2, mir-252_6	spermatogenesis	metal ion binding [GO:0,046,872]
Protein-L-isoaspartate (D-aspartate) O-methyltransferase domain containing 1	PCMTD1	mir-279_17, mir-1_38, mir-252_2, mir-252_6	protein modification process	methyltransferase activity [GO:0008168]
StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 4	STARD4	mir-1_38, mir-252_2, mir-252_6, mir-375_1	intracellular cholesterol transport [GO:0,032,367]	cholesterol binding [GO:0,015,485]
Transmembrane protein 168	TMEM168	mir-1_38, mir-X18, mir-375_4, mir-750_6	regulation of catabolic process [GO:0009894]; regulation of voltage-gated sodium channel activity [GO:1,905,150]	sodium channel regulator activity [GO:0,017,080]
Tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type (EC 3.1.3.48)	PTPN4	mir-279_17, mir-252_2, mir-252_6, mir-X18, mir-375_4	protein modification process [GO:0,036,211]	cytoskeletal protein binding [GO:0,008,092]; protein tyrosine phosphatase activity [GO:0,004,725]
YME1 like 1 ATPase	YME1L1	mir-1_38, mir-252_2, mir-252_6, mir-750_6	proteolysis [GO:0,006,508]	ATP binding [GO:0,005,524]; ATP hydrolysis activity [GO:0,016,887]; ATP-dependent peptidase activity [GO:0,004,176]; metalloendopeptidase activity [GO:0,004,222]

Some specific assays for miRNA target validation, such as the luciferase reporter gene and inhibitory or silencing assays have been carried out for several ixodid species. These assays allow researchers to validate the predicted miRNA target genes and thus confirm the regulatory mechanisms in which these miRNAs are involved. Assays conducted for *H. longicornis* have shown that mir-375, present in its saliva and salivary glands, regulates oviposition and hatching (Malik et al., 2019a). Similarly, mir-184 and mir-275 target vitellogenin mRNA and affect blood digestion and oviposition, and mir-2 acts on cuticular protein CPR1 and inhibits moulting (Hao et al., 2017; Malik et al., 2019b; Liu et al., 2020). In *Hyalomma anatolicum* and *Hyalomma asiaticum*, mir-1 and let-7 act on HSP60 and ecdysteroid receptor mRNAs, respectively, and are critical for normal tick development, fecundity, egg hatching and moulting (Wu et al., 2019; Luo et al., 2021). In *Dermacentor silvarum*, mir-2 and mir-279 target glycogen phosphorylase and serine genes, respectively, and are involved in regulating the cold response process of ticks (Agwunobi et al., 2021). We identified these above-mentioned miRNAs in the saliva of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata*. Therefore, we suppose that they would perform similar functions in argasid ticks, although this eventuality needs to be confirmed experimentally.

To explore putative roles for the *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* salivary miRNAs in tick feeding, we performed functional analysis of their predicted target genes in the swine host. We performed target prediction for the eight miRNA sequences (four per species) that showed the highest expression levels and that we had validated with RT-qPCR. All of them – mir-1_38, mir-750_6, mir-279_17 and mir-252_6 from *O. erraticus* and mir-252_2, mir-375_1, mir-375_4 and mir-X18 from *O. moubata* – have also been identified in the saliva of *I. ricinus* and *H. longicornis*, and the first seven have also been found in the salivary EVs of *H. longicornis* (Hackenberg et al., 2017; Malik et al., 2019a; Nawaz et al., 2020).

The *in silico* target prediction revealed that a particular miRNA can regulate numerous mRNAs through a miRNA–mRNA interaction, and

that a single mRNA can be controlled by several miRNAs (Riolo et al., 2020). In this study, we only analysed gene targets predicted by the four algorithms used and paid special attention to the genes/proteins that were targeted by at least four of the eight miRNAs tested (Table 2). The results of this analysis revealed that several host target proteins would be involved in relevant biological processes in tick–host relationships such as signal transduction, regulation of mRNA transcription and gene expression, synapse regulation, immune response, angiogenesis and vascular development. Specifically, the proteins TRAF-interacting protein (*TIFA* gene), growth hormone secretagogue receptor (*GHSR* gene) and protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type (*PTPN4* gene) would be involved in the regulation of host immune response. *TIFA* regulates nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) signaling and is critical for transducing intracellular signal to generate an inflammatory immune response that recruits immune cells to sites of bacterial infection or tissue damage (Niederhorn et al., 2020). *GHSR* is usually related with metabolic diseases, cardiac function, muscular mass and cancer. However, recently a new perspective about the presence of GSH-R in immune cells suggests that it might have a role in innate and adaptive immunity (Noh et al., 2022). In fact, it is known that in mice, the absence of GSH-R reduced pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 (Ma et al., 2013). *PTPN4* protein has also been identified as a specific inhibitor of the Toll-like receptor (TIR)-domain-containing adapter-inducing interferon- β -dependent toll-like receptor 4 pathway (Huai et al., 2015). Consequently, these proteins play a pivotal role in immune homeostasis, as they are involved in innate immune signaling and have important roles in both innate and adaptive immunity, associated with macrophage functional programming and T cell activation (Huai et al., 2015; Niederhorn et al., 2020; Noh et al., 2022). Taking the above into account, it is possible that the regulation of these genes by certain salivary miRNAs could facilitate and enable the blood uptake by ticks through the reduction of the inflammatory response at the feeding

site.

5. Conclusions

This is the first study to identify the salivary miRNAs in argasid ticks and to predict their potential target mRNAs in their host. Using miRNA-seq and RT-qPCR, we demonstrated that the saliva of *O. erraticus* and *O. moubata* contains dozens of miRNAs common to these argasids and several ixodid tick species. miRNA target gene prediction in the swine host and functional analysis of predicted targets strongly suggest that these non-protein molecules may be important players at the tick–host interface. This study opens doors to further investigation on non-protein players at the tick–host–pathogen interface, including prediction and experimental validation of miRNA targets in both the host and the own parasite. The results of these future investigations may instruct the rational selection of tick molecular targets for the development of new therapeutic and immune interventions aimed at controlling tick infestations and tick-borne pathogens.

Animal welfare statement

The procedures for tick feeding and experimentation with rabbits were approved by the Ethical and Animal Welfare Committee of the Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiology (IRNASA) and the Ethical Committee of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC, Spain) (Permit Number 742/2017).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ana Laura Cano-Argüelles: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ricardo Pérez-Sánchez:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Ana Oleaga:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

We deposited raw sequence reads in the NCBI under Bioproject accession number PRJNA931918 and BioSample accessions: SAMN33103033, SAMN33103032, SAMN33103031, SAMN33103030, SAMN33103029, and SAMN33103028. The Short read project were deposited under the SRA Accessions: SRR23347806, SRR23347807, SRR23347808, SRR23347809, SRR23347810, and SRR23347811.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.ttbdis.2023.102249.

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